

Residue Contact Graphs of Protein–Peptide Complexes

1BE9
115 residues | 557 contacts | 15 interface

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1JWG
560 residues | 5760 contacts | 29 interface

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1NX1
692 residues | 7026 contacts | 39 interface

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2EGN
83 residues | 387 contacts | 4 interface

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Nodes: protein residues | Edges: residue center-of-mass contacts $\leq 8 \text{ \AA}$ | Red: interface residues | Blue: non-interface residues | Node size: contact degree

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